

The Hypothetic Nutrient Constraint to Continuously Maintain as Gradient from Gastrula to Postnatal Development: An Important Mechanism for Recapitulation

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Abstract:

It was suggested by Cai a theory that the nutrient gradient differentiate the cellular living states to form the three germ layers of animal embryonic gastrula differential developing to three different subsequent fates, with the endoderm manifesting cellular living states in nutritious condition and forming the epithelium of digestive and respiratory system; the ectoderm manifesting cellular living states of nutrient dependence and environmental effects, and giving rise to the nervous and epithelial tissues; the mesoderm lying between them and forming the muscle and adipose. In parallel, it was also complied with the regulation of nutrients on various cultured stem cells. In this article, to account for these phenomena, it is extended this theory

and suggested that there be a constraint maintaining such nutrient gradient from gastrula to postnatal development continuously, due to the animals necessarily to deal with the nutritional transport and environmental effects being the same across all developmental stages after gastrula, for most animals before the appearance of rigid eggshell in evolution. It is the nutrient constraint forming gradient at gastrula that coordinates the development of all animals into fixed nutrient gradient as the most primitive animal of gastrula, recapitulating the developmental program at gastrula. In contrast, it is unnecessary for all animals universally to deal with nutritional transport before gastrula, generating evolutionary diversity in early embryonic stages before gastrula, as well as violations to Haeckel's recapitulation.

Keywords: *Gastrula, Trilaminar Germ Layers, Nutrient, Recapitulation.*

Introduction

Embryonic development in animals has been a complex subject yet to be solved fully. The most complex subject of animal development concerns the relationship between development and evolution, and has attracted the attention of many scientists (Bininda-Emonds, et al., 2002; Cai, 2024a; Minelli, 2005; Uesaka, et al., 2022), mostly concerning about the later stages of development (Cai, 2024a; Minelli, 2005; Uesaka, et al., 2022).

The early embryonic stages in animals manifest diverse and various, which challenges the universality of Haeckel's hypothesis of recapitulation (Bininda-Emonds, et al., 2002; Kuroda, et al., 2016; Raff, 1992). However, the partially differentiated trilaminar germ layers at the stage of gastrula are conserved in all animals of gastrula (Cai, 2016,2024b). To account for such evolutionary conservation of trilaminar germ layers at gastrula, Cai suggested a theory that a nutrient gradient exist in the three germ

layers of gastrula and partially differentiate the cellular living states there (Cai, 2016,2024b). In this article, it will be briefly reviewed to introduce and support this theory, and then to extend the nutrient gradient in this theory to become the developmental constraint from gastrula to postnatal development.

The Nutrient Gradient at Gastrula and Supports

The Theory of Nutrient Gradient at Gastrula

The gastrula is universally present in almost all animals except the very primitive coelenterates which are diploblastica. Most animals, including platyhelminthes, annelids, arthropods, vertebrates and so on, share the common embryonic stage as gastrula of three germ layers(Cai, 2016,2024b). Organogenesis begins from the three germ layers of gastrula to generate various organs in animals(Cai, 2016,2024a,2024b).

In 2016, Cai suggested a theory that a nutrient gradient exist in the three germ layers of gastrula and partially differentiate the cellular living states there, with the endoderm manifesting rich in nutritious condition, ectoderm manifesting nutrient dependence and environmental effects, and mesoderm manifesting intermediate between them (Cai, 2016,2024b).

The Trilaminar Developmental Fates to Support Nutrient Gradient at Gastrula

During early embryonic development, zygote cleavage generates the morula and then blastula. Embryonic cells of blastula undergo complex movement and invagination, and generate the gastrula of conserved trilaminar structure as the endoderm, ectoderm and mesoderm (Cai, 2016,2024b). At this stage, intercellular inductive signals other than nutrients begin to affect (Cai, 2024a). The gastrula starts organogenesis to generate various organs (Cai, 2024a).

As the partial differentiation of cells in the trilaminar gastrula forms the postulated nutrient gradient to direct the cell fates, the developmental outcomes of three layers of

gastrula can certainly be adopted to prove the correctness of the theory.

The endodermal cells in gastrula lie innermost in embryo, and most adjacent to the nutrients in gradient. To adapt to the nutritious condition, the pluripotent cells must express genes to digest and transform the nutrients, and synthesize glucose, amino acids and so on to supply other embryonic cells. In this regard, these cells rich in nutrients are coordinated toward such living states of cells, which imprints onto the subsequent organogenesis. During organogenesis, the endodermal cells in gastrula indeed differentiate and give rise to the epithelial lining of the digestive tract, associated glands and respiratory system in vertebrates(Fukuda, & Kikuchi, 2005; Rubin, 2007), as well as in *Drosophila*(Nakagoshi, 2005; Rubin, 2007), fitting well with the nutritious condition of the developmental outcomes of phenotype.

The ectodermal cells in gastrula lie outmost in embryo, and most distant to nutrients in gradient. To adapt to the relatively outmost environment, the pluripotent cells must rely more on other cells for nutrient supply, and express genes for sensation of and protection against the relatively environmental effects, such as more keratins, primitive neuronal characters and so on. These cells are coordinated toward such living states of nutrient dependence and environmental effects, which imprints onto the subsequent organogenesis. During organogenesis, the ectodermal cells give rise to neural progenitors for generating neural system in the dorsal side and epidermal progenitors for forming epidermal cells in the ventral side in vertebrates(Chang, & Hemmati-Brivanlou, 1998; Moreau, & Leclerc, 2004), while also give rise to neural cells(Campos-Ortega, 1995; Stüttem, & Campos-Ortega, 1991) and epidermal cuticle in *Drosophila*(Campos-Ortega, 1995; Payre, 2004), fitting with the nutrient dependence and environmental effects of the developmental outcomes of phenotype.

The mesodermal cells in gastrula lie between the endoderm and ectoderm. To adapt to the moderate condition, the pluripotent cells must express genes to use and transform nutrients, use

or store energy, and so on. These cells are coordinated toward such living states of moderate nutrients and conditions, which imprints onto the subsequent organogenesis. During organogenesis, the cells of embryonic mesoderm give rise to muscles (Pourquié, 2001,2003) and adipose tissues(Han, et al., 2011) in vertebrates, and to muscles in

Drosophila(Junion, & Jagla, 2022; Nguyen, & Frasch, 2006), fitting with the moderate nutrients and conditions of the developmental outcomes of phenotype.

Table 1 outlines the developmental fates of trilaminar germ layers of gastrula.

Table1. The Developmental Fates of Trilaminar Germ Layers of Gastrula

	Endoderm	Mesoderm	Ectoderm
Developmental Fates in Vertebrates	Digestive tract and glands, respiratory system	Muscles, and adipose tissues	Neural system and epidermal cells
Developmental Fates in Drosophila	Digestive tract and glands	Muscles	Neural cells and epidermal cuticle
Relationship with Nutrient during Development	Absorption and transformation of nutrient being maintained throughout development	Usage, transformation and storage of nutrient and energy being maintained throughout development	Usage of nutrient supply from others being maintained throughout development

The Stem Cell Culture to Support Nutrient Gradient at Gastrula

Cultures of stem cells can also manifest the trilaminar differentiation of embryonic cells in response to nutrient gradient. It was reported that activation of amino acid response through limitation of them in culture favored the primitive endodermal, visceral endodermal, and endodermal lineages, whereas suppressed the mesodermal and certain ectodermal lineages(Shan, et al., 2013), demonstrating the endodermal tendency to transform and supply nutrients including amino acids. In contrary, cultured *Xenopus* presumptive ectoderm was made successful in long term in a nutrient-supplemented culture medium(Fukui, et al., 2003), while cultured neural progenitor cells were usually promoted in proliferation in vitro with hypoxia(Hegewald, et al., 2011; Zhu, et al., 2011), demonstrating the ectodermal direction to use supplied nutrients from others and respond to environmental stress. Besides, mesoderm-specific transcript was shown to be associated with fat mass expansion in response to positive energy balance(Nikonova, et al., 2008), suggesting the mesodermal direction to use nutrients and store energy. In these respects, stem cell cultures strongly support the gradient of nutrients to regulate the living states of

embryonic cells, demonstrating the endodermal cells to absorb, transform and supply nutrients, the mesodermal cells to use, transform and store nutrients and energy, as well as the ectodermal cells to rely on nutrient supply and respond to environmental stress.

The Nutrient Constraint to Maintain Gradient from Gastrula to Postnatal Development

For the universal presence of nutrient gradient and trilaminar gastrula in both vertebrates and invertebrates, there is obvious an intrinsic constraint or evolutionary pressure responsible for the conservation of nutrient gradient and trilaminar gastrula.

As demonstrated above and briefly outlined in Table 1, the endodermal cells rich in nutrients differentiate and give rise to the epithelial lining of the digestive tract, associated glands and respiratory system in vertebrates(Fukuda, & Kikuchi, 2005; Rubin, 2007), as well as in *Drosophila*(Nakagoshi, 2005; Rubin, 2007), with the endodermal cells and their postnatal developmental outcomes of phenotype both fitting well with the nutritious condition while

maintaining functional as absorption and transformation of nutrients.

The ectodermal cells distant to nutrients in gradient but closest to the environment give rise to neural progenitors for generating neural system in the dorsal side and epidermal progenitors for forming epidermal cells in the ventral side in vertebrates (Chang, & Hemmati-Brivanlou, 1998; Moreau, & Leclerc, 2004), while also give rise to neural cells (Campos-Ortega, 1995; Stüttem, & Campos-Ortega, 1991) and epidermal cuticle in *Drosophila* (Campos-Ortega, 1995; Payre, 2004), with the ectodermal cells and their postnatal developmental outcomes of phenotype both fitting well with such nutritional/environmental condition while maintaining usage of nutrient supply from others.

The mesodermal cells in gastrula, lying between endoderm and ectoderm, give rise to muscles (Pourquié, 2001, 2003) and adipose tissues (Han, et al., 2011) in vertebrates, and to muscles in *Drosophila* (Junion, & Jagla, 2022; Nguyen, & Frasch, 2006), with the mesodermal cells and their postnatal developmental outcomes of phenotype both fitting with the moderate nutrients and conditions while maintaining functional as transformation, usage and storage of nutrients and energy.

In these regards, it is obvious that the functions of endoderm, ectoderm and mesoderm to deal with nutrient are maintained in the same as their corresponding postnatal outcomes of phenotype during embryonic development after gastrula. Therefore, with such obvious supports, herein it is extended the theory of nutrient gradient to that, because the animals need deal with the nutritional transport and environmental effects being the same across all developmental stages after gastrula, it is an intrinsic constraint to maintain the nutrient gradient from gastrula to postnatal development continuously.

It is noted that the embryonic environment may be different from postnatal developmental animals, especially in viviparous mammals, and in birds or reptiles of rigid eggshell. However, for most animals before and including amphibians in evolution, the eggs are not

protected by rigid eggshell, while are exposed to environment directly, just like the postnatal animals. Thus, the ectodermal environmental effects are also maintained the same for most animals before the appearance of rigid eggshell for birds or reptiles in evolution.

The Nutrient Constraint Forming Gradient at Gastrula as Important Cause of Recapitulation

Haeckel's Recapitulation

Ernst Haeckel hypothesized the idea of sequence heterochrony and recapitulation, with embryogenesis of an animal paralleling its own phylogenetic history, sequential developing from more ancestral features to more derived ones (Bininda-Emonds, et al., 2002; Clune, et al., 2012), while recent rectifications confined it more to the later organogenetic stages (Uesaka, et al., 2022). Changes to early developmental stages were suggested by recapitulation as selected against because they tended to disrupt the later developmental program (Bininda-Emonds, et al., 2002; Clune, et al., 2012).

Many exceptions have accumulated to recapitulation to make it not universal. The change in early spatial organization of existing animal morphogenesis, such as *Lymnaea stagnalis* (Kuroda, et al., 2016), is not compatible with sequential recapitulation of Haeckel (Bininda-Emonds, et al., 2002). Besides, duplication of morphogenetic program might also occur at earlier stages, such as duplication of segments (Minelli, 2005). All these spatial change or duplication of early stage can make use of existing developmental program and termination in later stages (Cai, 2024a).

Nutrient Constraint Forming Gradient at Gastrula as Important Cause of Recapitulation

As demonstrated above, with obvious supports, it is an intrinsic constraint to maintain the nutrient gradient from gastrula to postnatal development continuously, because the animals need deal with the nutritional transport and

environmental effects being the same across all developmental stages after gastrula.

In this regard, the nutrient constraint forming gradient from gastrula to postnatal development will coordinate the development of all animals of gastrula into fixed programs along the nutrient gradient of endoderm, mesoderm and ectoderm, with the embryonic development at gastrula fixed to the most primitive animal of trilaminar germ layers, recapitulating the developmental program at gastrula of these ancestral animals. Thus, the nutrient constraint forming gradient is an important mechanism causing Haeckel's recapitulation at gastrula, and directly supports Haeckel's recapitulation.

Exceptions to Recapitulation from Embryonic Stages Earlier Than Gastrula

Unlike the universal nutrient gradient existing in three layers of gastrula(Cai, 2016,2024b), it is not necessary for all animals universally to deal with nutritional transport before gastrula, generating evolutionary diversity in early embryonic stages before gastrula.

In most animals, the earlier partially differentiated vegetal hemisphere full of nutrients and animal hemisphere full of dividing

cells(Escobar-Aguirre, et al., 2017; Sardet, et al., 2004) correspond to the respective endoderm and ectoderm of gastrula on cellular living states of nutrients(Cai, 2024b; Escobar-Aguirre, et al., 2017; Sardet, et al., 2004). However, exceptions arise from embryonic movement and reorganization, including invagination, involution, ingression, and so on, to change the cellular environment of nutrition in some animals, such as *Drosophila* with endoderm forming exceptionally from oocyte polarity and embryonic invagination instead of vegetal hemisphere(Stathopoulos, & Newcomb, 2020).

The evolutionary diversity in early embryonic stages before gastrula violates the Haeckel's recapitulation, because evolutionary changes occurred in stages earlier than the conserved gastrula stage, with ontogeny obviously not recapitulating phylogeny. Variations in embryonic stages earlier than gastrula are the important causes of violations to Haeckel's recapitulation.

Table 2 summarizes the relationship among the three parts as the nutrient constraint forming gradient at gastrula, variations in embryonic stages earlier than gastrula and Haeckel's recapitulation

Table 2. Relationship among Nutrient Constraint Forming Gradient at Gastrula, Embryonic Variations before Gastrula and Haeckel's Recapitulation

	Nutrient Constraint Forming Gradient at Gastrula	Embryonic Variations before Gastrula
Haeckel's Recapitulation	Recapitulation by fixing nutrient gradient at gastrula as the most primitive animal of gastrula	Violations to Haeckel's recapitulation due to evolutionary changes in early embryonic stages before conserved gastrula

Conclusion

In this article, it is briefly introduced the new theory that a nutrient gradient exist in the three germ layers of gastrula and partially differentiate the cellular living states there. The theory is well supported by the subsequent developmental fates of three layers of gastrula, with the endodermal cells responding to nutritious condition and giving rise to the epithelium of digestive tract, associated glands and respiratory system in both vertebrates and *Drosophila*; the

ectodermal cells relying on extrinsic nutrients and responding to environmental effects, and giving rise to the neural and epidermal cells in vertebrates and *Drosophila*; the mesoderm lying between the endoderm and ectoderm, and giving rise to the muscle and adipose tissues in vertebrates, and muscles in *Drosophila*. Nutrient and oxygen manipulations in various stem cell cultures also support the nutrient gradient as a key regulatory factor after embryonic gastrulation.

In this article, to explain these phenomena, it is extended this theory and further suggested that there be a constraint maintaining such nutrient gradient from gastrula to postnatal development continuously, because the animals need deal with the nutritional transport and environmental effects being the same across all developmental stages after gastrula, for most animals before the later appearance of rigid eggshell in evolution. It is the nutrient constraint forming gradient at gastrula that coordinates the development of all animals of gastrula into fixed nutrient gradient as the most primitive animal of gastrula, recapitulating the developmental program at gastrula. However, it is not necessary for all animals universally to deal with nutritional transport before gastrula, generating evolutionary diversity in early embryonic stages before gastrula, while causing violations to Haeckel's recapitulation.

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Authors' Contributions

The sole one author responsible for all of the article.

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References

- Bininda-Emonds, O.R.P., Jeffery, J.E., Coates, M.I., & Richardson, M.K. (2002). From Haeckel to event-pairing: the evolution of developmental sequences. *Theory in Biosciences*, 121, 297–320. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12064-002-0016-5>.
- Cai, Z.-J. (2016). Regulation of both cell state and gene expression with nutrient gradient as conserved mechanism differentiating the cell fates for embryonic gastrulation: A theory. *Open Access Library Journal*, 3, e2348. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1102348>.
- Cai, Z.-J. (2024a). The spatial constraint requiring organogenetic termination: Supplemental to Haeckel and von Baer for development and evolution. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(3), 504-516. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(3\).39](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(3).39).
- Cai, Z.-J. (2024b). Partial Differentiation of Cellular Living State for Nutrient Gradient in Gastrula of Animal Development. *Innovations in Biological Science*, 10, 73-83. <https://doi.org/10.9734/bpi/ibs/v10/1807>.
- Campos-Ortega, J.A. (1995). Genetic mechanisms of early neurogenesis in *Drosophila melanogaster*. *Molecular Neurobiology*, 10(2-3), 75-89. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02740668>.
- Chang, C., & Hemmati-Brivanlou, A. (1998). Cell fate determination in embryonic ectoderm. *Journal of Neurobiology*, 36, 128-151. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-4695\(199808\)36:2<128::AID-NEU3>3.0.CO;2-3](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-4695(199808)36:2<128::AID-NEU3>3.0.CO;2-3).
- Clune, J., Pennock, R.T., Ofria, C., & Lenski, R.E. (2012). Ontogeny tends to recapitulate phylogeny in digital organisms. *The American Naturalist*, 180, E54-63. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jez.b.23027>.
- Escobar-Aguirre, M., Elkouby, Y.M., & Mullins, M.C. (2017). Localization in oogenesis of maternal regulators of embryonic development. *Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology*, 953, 173-207. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-46095-6_5.

- Fukuda, K., & Kikuchi, Y. (2005). Endoderm development in vertebrates: fate mapping, induction and regional specification. *Development, Growth & Differentiation*, 47, 343-355. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1440-169X.2005.00815.x>.
- Fukui, Y., Furue, M., Myoishi, Y., Sato, J.D., Okamoto, T., & Asashima, M. (2003). Long-term culture of *Xenopus* presumptive ectoderm in a nutrient-supplemented culture medium. *Development, Growth & Differentiation*, 45, 499-506. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1440-169x.2003.00717.x>.
- Han, J., Lee, J.E., Jin, J., Lim, J.S., Oh, N., Kim, K., Chang, S.I., Shibuya, M., Kim, H., & Koh, G.Y. (2011). The spatiotemporal development of adipose tissue. *Development*, 138, 5027-5037. <https://doi.org/10.1242/dev.067686>.
- Hegewald, C., Alt, R., Hetz, S., Cross, M., Acikgoez, A., Till, H., Metzger, R., & Metzger, M. (2011). Reduced oxygen stress promotes propagation of murine postnatal enteric neural progenitors in vitro. *Neurogastroenterology and Motility*, 23, e412-424. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2982.2011.01761.x>.
- Junion, G., & Jagla, K. (2022). Diversification of muscle types in *Drosophila* embryos. *Experimental Cell Research*, 410(1), 112950. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yexcr.2021.112950>.
- Kuroda, R., Fujikura, K., Abe, M., Hosoiri, Y., Asakawa, S., Shimizu, M., Umeda, S., Ichikawa, F., & Takahashi, H. (2016). Diaphanous gene mutation affects spiral cleavage and chirality in snails. *Scientific Reports*, 6, 34809. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep34809>.
- Minelli, A. (2005). A morphologist's perspective on terminal growth and segmentation. *Evolution & Development*, 7, 568-573. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1525-142X.2005.05060.x>.
- Moreau, M., & Leclerc, C. (2004). The choice between epidermal and neural fate: a matter of calcium. *International Journal Of Developmental Biology*, 48(2-3), 75-84. <https://doi.org/10.1387/ijdb.15272372>.
- Nakagoshi, H. (2005). Functional specification in the *Drosophila* endoderm. *Development, Growth & Differentiation*, 47, 383-392. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1440-169X.2005.00811.x>.
- Nguyen, H.T., & Frasch, M. (2006). MicroRNAs in muscle differentiation: lessons from *Drosophila* and beyond. *Current Opinion in Genetics & Development*, 16, 533-539. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gde.2006.08.010>.
- Nikonova, L., Koza, R.A., Mendoza, T., Chao, P.M., Curley, J.P., & Kozak, L.P. (2008). Mesoderm-specific transcript is associated with fat mass expansion in response to a positive energy balance. *The FASEB Journal*, 22, 3925-3937. <https://doi.org/10.1096/fj.08-108266>.
- Payre, F. (2004). Genetic control of epidermis differentiation in *Drosophila*. *The International Journal of Developmental Biology*, 48, 207-215. <https://doi.org/10.1387/ijdb.15272387>.
- Pourquié, O. (2001). Vertebrate somitogenesis. *Annual Review of Cell and Developmental Biology*, 17, 311-350. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.cellbio.17.1.311>.
- Pourquié, O. (2003). Vertebrate somitogenesis: a novel paradigm for animal segmentation? *International Journal of Developmental Biology*, 47(7-8), 597-603.
- Raff, R.A. (1992). Direct-developing sea urchins and the evolutionary reorganization of early development. *Bioessays*, 14, 211-218. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bies.950140403>.
- Rubin, D.C. (2007). Intestinal morphogenesis. *Current Opinion in Gastroenterology*, 23(2), 111-114. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MOG.0b013e3280145082>.
- Sardet, C., Prodon, F., Prulière, G., & Chenevert, J. (2004). Polarization of eggs and embryos: some common principles. *Médecine Sciences(Paris)*, 20(4), 414-23. <https://doi.org/10.1051/medsci/2004204414>.
- Shan, J., Hamazaki, T., Tang, T.A., Terada, N., & Kilberg, M.S. (2013). Activation of the amino acid response modulates lineage specification during differentiation of murine embryonic stem

cells. *American Journal of Physiology-Endocrinology and Metabolism*, 305, E325-335. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpendo.00136.2013>.

Stathopoulos, A., & Newcomb, S. (2020). Setting up for gastrulation: *D. melanogaster*. *Current Topics in Developmental Biology*, 136: 3-32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.ctdb.2019.11.004>.

Stüttem, I., & Campos-Ortega, J.A. (1991). Cell commitment and cell interactions in the ectoderm of *Drosophila melanogaster*. *Development*, Suppl 2, 39-46.

Uesaka, M., Kuratani, S., & Irie, N. (2022). The developmental hourglass model and recapitulation: An attempt to integrate the two models. *Journal of Experimental Zoology Part B-Molecular and Developmental Evolution*, 338(1-2), 76-86. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jez.b.23027>.

Zhu, L.L., Zhao, T., Huang, X., Liu, Z.H., Wu, L.Y., Wu, K.W., & Fan, M. (2011). Gene expression profiles and metabolic changes in embryonic neural progenitor cells under low oxygen. *Cellular Reprogramming*, 13, 113-120. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cell.2010.0043>.